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Processing of multiple facility data in common pipelines

WP26: JRA1 – Maximizing the output of fragment screening

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D77 (D26.6): Processing of multiple facility data in common pipelines

Lead beneficiary: NKI

Involved partners: NKI, DIAMOND, EMBL-GR, EMBL-EBI, HZB, MAX IV

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1 Introduction

This iNEXT-Discovery deliverable, D78/D26.6 from JRA1 (WP26: “Maximizing the output of fragment screening”), describes the processing of screening data in common pipelines at physically different locations. Within the consortium, partners use different software pipelines to perform consecutive steps of fragment screening against protein targets that might benefit from interconnectivity. To get a glance, for focussing on crystallographic fragment screening we distinguish the following processes: Data collection and processing, Fragment fitting, Model optimisation, Hit analysis, and Deposition.

1.1 Crystallography data pipelines and other tools

For data collection and processing, each screening facility has its own pipeline, for instance Dimple¹ at DIAMOND and Pipedream² at EMBL-GR. For fragment fitting, the screening facilities have in-house pipelines such as RHOFIT³ at EMBL-GR and PanDDA⁴ at DIAMOND. PDB-REDO⁵, the crystallography 3D structure refinement software developed and hosted by partner NKI, can also fit fragments but is less mature than RHOFIT and PanDDA for this functionality. Optimised procedures for fragment fitting in PDB-REDO are currently being developed. Whereas model optimisation can be performed manually, the PDB-REDO pipeline is designed to do this in a fully automated fashion, which allows scaling up to many hundreds of models with fitted fragments. Sophisticated tools for hit analysis, for example DIAMOND’s Fragalysis⁶, do exist, but these are not yet automated to such a level that they can be considered a pipeline. Finally, partner EMBL-EBI provides an automated framework for data deposition to either the Protein Data Bank⁷ or the pilot screen repository (D26.10) they both host, and continues to collaborate with various screening facilities to make this procedure as efficient and homogeneous as possible.

1.2 Data exchange

Essential to the connection of multiple pipelines is robust data exchange. Therefore, based on consultation with consortium partners, all required (meta)data was identified and a data exchange standard was laid out (D26.5). This standard then formed the basis to design a single mmCIF-encoded^{8,9} data structure that captures this (meta)data directly or points to its location. While the final form of these so-called *investigation.cif* files is still being optimized by the parties involved, which will extend beyond the duration of the iNEXT-Discovery project, working examples can be obtained from the pilot repository for fragment screens located at https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/msd/fragment_screening/. In the following we describe how the commonly used PDB-REDO software has been adapted to handle locally staged screening data (Section 2); then how iNEXT-Discovery prepares for pipeline connections (Section 3).

2 Processing locally staged fragment screen data

2.1 Data from local screens

To optimise PDB-REDO for handling fragment screening data, copies of screens (or subsets thereof) were made available by different screening facilities (DIAMOND, EMBL-GR, HZB, MAX IV). Each screen consists of tens to many hundreds of data sets, successfully processed by a local data collection and processing pipeline. For each data set a crystallographic data file and

a structure model was provided, and a description of the used fragment was made available. It should be noted that the format of this fragment description currently still varies between screening facilities, but is planned to be standardised.

2.2 The PDB-REDO procedure

Given this input data, the PDB-REDO pipeline is applied to each individual dataset belonging to a screen, and depending on the requirements from the user, it enters one of two workflows:

1. Fragment fitting + model optimisation
 - i. Create restraints for the fragment
 - ii. Refine the initial structure model to improve the electron density maps
 - iii. Rebuild the structure model using the PDB-REDO rebuilding tools^{10–12}
 - iv. Fit the fragment, provided there is sufficient signal in the electron density
 - v. Optimise the model by additional refinement
2. Model optimisation only
 - i. Refine the initial structure model to improve the electron density maps
 - ii. Rebuild the structure model using the PDB-REDO rebuilding tools^{10–12}
 - iii. Optimise the model by additional refinement

The second workflow is meant for apo datasets (i.e. proteins in absence of fragment), or for models in which a fragment is already fitted by another fragment fitting pipeline.

The key output of the PDB-REDO pipeline is a new structural model, with fitted fragment if applicable, and a large set of metadata that, with respect to model quality, includes interaction information for any fragment or other ligand. Needless to add that all PDB-REDO output is in a FAIR and homogeneous form, even when coming from different sources.

2.3 Screen-scale data processing

The calculations that PDB-REDO performs on individual datasets from a particular fragment screen are fully independent, which makes the processing of entire screening campaigns *embarrassingly parallel*. That is, a screen can be processed with N datasets simultaneously, provided there are N CPU threads available. To assist such parallel processing a series of wrappers were written to process screens coming from different facilities, tailored to the specific way their data is presented, e.g. in terms of directory structure and the format of the fragment descriptions (see MS39). In the near future, once the screen data is provided through *investigation.cif* files, these case-specific wrappers will be replaced by a single one.

Currently, all calculations can be performed on local hardware, but should the need arise this can also be scaled out to cloud resources, for instance through the European Open Science Cloud. The PDB-REDO pipeline contains a large selection of NKI-made and 3rd-party software, which makes it not straightforward to deploy, but the entire pipeline has recently been containerised to enable calculations also outside the institute. Notably, despite the complexity of the software, the hardware requirements are rather modest and do not require high-power GPUs or large amounts of RAM.

3 Design for processing pipelines from multiple facilities

In previous section we described the processing of locally staged data, yet in the larger picture a user should not need to worry about staging their data. Instead, facilities should be able to

pass fragment screens for processing with minimal user effort. While the implementation of this development is still ongoing, we are already able to give a description of its design, using model optimisation in PDB-REDO of a screen with fitted fragments as an illustrative example.

3.1 Setting up a single model optimisation

Fragments are typically fitted at the screening facilities using pipelines such as RHOFIT and PanDDA. To improve downstream analysis of potential hits, especially models binding fragments should be refined and rebuilt as well as possible. To this end, multiple procedures exist ranging from ‘interactive model tuning’ to fully automated pipelines. As a well-established case of the latter, PDB-REDO typically runs through a web server or as locally installed software. Local deployment is not suited for current streamlining purposes as it requires screening facilities or users to deploy and maintain the pipeline themselves, which is time consuming mainly due to regular updates. The webserver takes away these deployment and maintenance requirements, but is by design interactive via a user-interface, and not suited for automation.

During the iNEXT-Discovery project, the PDB-REDO website engine was completely redesigned. As a pre-emptive to allow automation of screening analyses (Section 3.2), it integrates a webservice where calculations can be setup via an API that takes the current model, the crystallographic data and any restraints for fitted fragments as input. Apart from running standard refinement calculations through an interface convenient for automation, this API also allows the fine-tuning of PDB-REDO parameters, including setting up ligand and fragment fitting. These additional settings are passed to the API as a JSON data structure. This functionality for experts is purposely not available through the webserver, as the latter targets less experienced crystallographers.

The results of a PDB-REDO calculation are provided as a self-contained web component. This ensures that the output can easily be integrated into user interfaces from different screening facilities, furthermore, this web component design is meant to be maintenance-free for facilities. Any updates to PDB-REDO output happen inside the web component, not in the way it is integrated. The PDB-REDO API is already in active use, being integrated in the CCP4i2 and CCP4-Cloud interfaces of the CCP4 suite¹³. The API is documented on <https://pdb-redo.eu/api-doc> and the code is available via <https://github.com/PDB-REDO/pdb-redo-session-manager> under a BSD-2-Clause license.

3.2 Full screen design

A challenge for full screening campaign analysis is how to efficiently set up tens-hundreds of calculations for data coming from a screening facility. Rather than setting up individual PDB-REDO calculations, an entire screen should be processed as such. Here, too, the *investigation.cif* file provides a solution, and once this file format is in its optimised, final form, a new API will be implemented that uses a single *investigations.cif* file as input, together with an optional JSON file describing any non-standard PDB-REDO settings that are needed. The *investigation.cif* file will then be used by a wrapper program to locate and download the input data required for individual PDB-REDO runs. The same wrapper will also manage these individual runs and collate the results into a new *investigation.cif* file. This file should also describe where the output can be collected by the user.

3.3 Data security

Data security is an important consideration in the running of off-site pipelines because data, including fragment screening output, are considered proprietary at least until they are published. To facilitate data security the PDB-REDO API uses token-based authentication procedures that allows only registered users to securely upload and download their files. This mechanism will be extended to the API for passing whole screens to PDB-REDO. Screening facilities will decide on whether they want to use a facility account for user screens (either one newly generated for each screen, or a single one for a set of screens), or let the user use their own PDB-REDO credentials. In either way, this design does not cover the collection of data that are described in the input *investigation.cif* file from the screening facility. To overcome this, we foresee several solutions:

- The data are temporarily staged by individual facilities in a ‘security-through-obscurity’ manner. Although perhaps not ideal, the risk of data leakage is very small. Also, this method is easy to implement and will not require changes to the *investigations.cif* format.
- Facilities and PDB-REDO may pre-arrange credentials (e.g. public/private keys) so that the PDB-REDO server (backend) can connect safely to a facility. If this method is consistent for all facilities, there is no need to change the *investigations.cif* format, otherwise it should be clear at which facility certain data are staged. This information can be part of the *investigations.cif* file, which requires a format amendment, or it can be part of the API call which is easier to implement.
- The authentication method and credentials are passed as part of the API call that screening facilities use to start a PDB-REDO calculation. This approach can be part of the implementation of the API and is therefore at the moment the preferred option.

4 Future perspectives

Although many prerequisites are met and great progress has been made to accomplish ‘processing of multiple facility data in common pipelines’, there is still some work to do to transparently connect the pipelines hosted at different partners. First of all the *investigations.cif* format will be finalised, upon which the PDB-REDO API call and new screen wrapper can be implemented. In parallel, any screening facility can implement data staging and, if desired, an authentication mechanism. When this is completed, the pipelines can be connected, similarly to how the current PDB-REDO API was integrated into the CCP4 suite.

Notably, independent of their ongoing PDB-REDO developments, the NKL software developers recently decided to create a new method for fragment fitting. This will be even more sophisticated than current approach described above, but is beyond the scope of achieving this deliverable.

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